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WHY CONDUCT ENGLISH PROFICIENCY TEST?

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According to the Board of Investments, one of the Philippines' greatest advantages is the availability of high-caliber human resources. "Our people have an excellent education. We are one of the largest English-speaking countries in the world since 94 percent of the population is literate.

Based on several assessments, the Philippines has the largest English-speaking population in the world, ranking anywhere from third to sixth. Even at a basic level, our talent pool is capable of speaking, reading, and writing in this language.

English proficiency is a competitive advantage that prior generations of Filipinos used to have, according to the Department of Education. According to Butch Hernandez, executive director of the Eggie Apostol Foundation, many recent high school or college graduates struggle to speak English, and occasionally even their native language, clearly and fluently.

Since teachers are regarded as the key factor in delivering education to pupils, the success or failure of students learning English depends greatly on them. Therefore, numerous studies demonstrating the worrying fall in English proficiency of the majority of pupils in both public and private schools have shown that it is related to the type of instruction being provided to them and, undoubtedly, the proficiency of the teachers in the language being taught.

The ability of teachers to communicate with and impart knowledge to their pupils may be constrained by their lack of confidence in their level of language proficiency. The process of learning a language is not linear; the four language skills of hearing, speaking, reading, and writing can be picked up at varying rates, with peaks and valleys along the way.

In this regard, administering the English Proficiency Test (EPT) to instructors is generally a desirable action for the reasons listed below:

1. It would assess the degree of English literacy and teaching abilities of the educators who play a crucial role in creating Filipinos who are globally competitive.
2. It will test the instructor's proficiency with both spoken and written American English.
3. It will help to clarify the difficulties involved in learning the English language.
4. It will establish how the assessment can aid in efficient instruction.
5. It will create genuine and trustworthy assessments that are most likely to produce crucial information about the acquisition of the English language.
6. It will assist the Department of Education's (DepED) test developers and testing program administrators in developing additional training and/or refresher courses

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aimed at bettering the English proficiency of both elementary and secondary school teachers and further preparing them with the necessary knowledge and skills.

Dr. Alonzo asserts that our future educators should ensure that English is taught as a tool for communication rather than as a body of knowledge to be absorbed. Similarly, the K-12 basic education frameworks are followed by the Department of Education, which places a priority on student needs and ensures that pupils acquire the English language holistically.

There are a number of suggestions to help Filipinos further their English language proficiency, though: 1) constant use and practice of the language could help to further solidify our economy; 2) there is still much room for improvement in terms of grammar, which could also help learners feel less anxious; and 3) there is a need to strike a balance between honing English language education and preserving our regional and cultural languages.

In educational institutions that seek to elevate the quality of English language teaching, teachers' proficiency in planning and implementing English classes to improve students' English proficiency, and curriculum developers' proficiency in creating cutting-edge English proficiency learning materials, must both be improved.

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